

HEALTH, FOOD SAFETY AND AGROECOLOGY

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Summary : Agroecology promotes health and food security as it is based on sustainable assumptions of production, rational use of the environment and preservation of agrobiodiversity, among others. The objective of the article is to reflect on the interfaces of agroecology with the rural environment, notably in the light of health promotion and food security. Methodologically, it is a qualitative research, with a bibliographical approach and uses a literature review to bring reflections on the problem, in the context of public health. A bibliographic review was carried out in the databases of *Science Direct* and Google Scholar articles. The results point to the relevance of agroecology and the close relationships between the topics addressed.

Keywords: Agroecology. Health. Food Security. Sustainable development

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic, which occurred due to the appearance of the SARS-CoV-2 virus, caused many global problems, aggravating social ills such as hunger, economic and social inequality, unemployment, violence, housing, access to health in a dignified and universal way, among others. (STROPARO, 2021; STROPARO, 2021A). In this sense, the search for sustainable solutions has raised discussions in the most diverse senses. Dealing specifically with hunger, food insecurity and solutions that promote health, agroecology emerges as one of the sustainable alternatives for the production of biodiverse foods, without the use of pesticides and with respect for local food traditions. (BEZNER KERR et al., 2021; HUSS et al., 2021; TITTONELL et al., 2021; FRISON; CLÉMENT, 2020; ALTIERI; NICHOLLS, 2020a; 2020b).

Research carried out by the Brazilian Network for Research in Sovereignty and Food Security (PENSSAN Network) and published through the document entitled “II National Survey on Food Insecurity in the Context of the Covid-19 Pandemic in Brazil”, points out that severe food insecurity affects 9 % of the population – that is, 19 million Brazilians are starving. The number of Brazilians who did not have full and permanent access to food reaches 116.8

million people, of which 43.4 million do not have enough food, which characterizes moderate or severe food insecurity. (REDE PENSSAN, 2022).

Poverty, hunger, malnutrition, inadequate diets, land degradation, water scarcity, social inequalities, loss of biodiversity and climate change are at the center of discussions that strive for sustainable development and are directly related to the way we produce food and treat of production resources. Combating hunger and guaranteeing access to safe, nutritionally dense food in adequate quantities, without seasonal fluctuations, has been the struggle of most organizations worldwide, as well as the keynote of an essential debate in favor of the adoption and encouragement of systems sustainable agrifood practices within the principles of agroecology, which is seen as an alternative for overcoming world food insecurity. (UNDP, 2021; ALTIERI & NICHOLLS, 2020; NICHOLLS & ALTIERI, 2018; STROPARO; FLORIANI, 2022).

Food insecurity and poverty are among the main causes of conflict, violence, migration and political instability (FAO, 2016). In this sense, and seeking solutions against unsustainability and food insecurity, there is a justification for the research that stems, therefore, from the indissociability of agroecology with health promotion, with the offer of varied, healthy and nutritionally dense foods with food security and consequent local development. (STROPARO and SOUZA, 2022; STROPARO, 2021a; ALTIERI; NICHOLLS, 2020; NICHOLLS; ALTIERI, 2018; TOMICH et al., 2011; FRISON; CLÉMENT, 2020).

However, the existing interfaces between health, food security and agroecology are much deeper and also refer to the process called "McDonaldization" where principles of *fast-food restaurants* became dominant, in opposition to local traditions of fresh food, varied and nutritionally dense. (RITZER, 1993). Therefore, food insecurity is not only the lack of food, conditioned by economic issues and vulnerabilities, but also the prioritization of industrialized, nutritionally poor foods, as well as sedentary habits and little care with the prevention of serious diseases such as obesity, for example.

METHODOLOGY

The research can be characterized as qualitative, with a bibliographical approach and uses a literature review to bring reflections on the problem. It is theoretically based on the concepts of agroecology, food security, health and sustainability. A bibliographic review was carried out in *Science Direct* and Google Scholar article databases. The articles were selected for convenience, respecting the relationship between the subject developed and the present theme.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Food and Nutritional Security (SAN), according to Law n. 11,346, of September 15, 2006, consists of realizing the right of everyone to regular and permanent access to quality food, in sufficient quantity, without compromising access to other essential needs, based on health-promoting eating practices that respect the cultural diversity and that are environmentally, culturally, economically and socially sustainable. (BRASIL, 2006). It refers to the right of peoples to decide their own food system and to produce healthy, culturally appropriate, accessible, sustainable and ecological food, placing those who produce, distribute and consume food at the heart of food systems and policies, above the requirements of market. (BRASIL, 2012). The concept encompasses, therefore, issues related to the production and availability of food, as well as the concern with the integral promotion of health, involving aspects of nutrition, health and socioeconomic status, which are inseparable.

In line with this, studies published by the *High Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition* (HLPE) in the document entitled “ *Agroecological and other innovative approaches for sustainable agriculture and food systems that enhance food security and nutrition* ” and “ *TAPE Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation* ” from FAO (2019), highlight the relationships between food security and agrifood systems, notably sustainable processes that are less invasive to the environment, which promote the safeguarding of biodiversity, care for biomes, with the social and community aspects of populations, aiming to health, well-being, quality of life and sustainability. (HLDE, 2019; FAO, 2019). Agrifood systems “consist of all elements (environment, people, inputs, processes, infrastructure, institutions, etc.) and activities related to the production, processing, distribution, preparation and consumption of food, and the results of these activities. (HLDE, 2019).

Food security exists when all people, at all times, have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food to meet their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life. (FAO, 1996). Currently, food and nutrition security considers energy, protein and nutrient needs for a healthy life (*Committee on World Food Security, 2012*) and is characterized under four approaches: food availability, access, use and stability. (EL BILALI, 2019)

It is understood that healthy eating is one of the pillars of health promotion and is inseparable from discussions on food sovereignty and sustainable development. In this way, the relationship between food safety and the food production process has been established, which excels in the diversity of products, in the preservation of the local food culture and other

assumptions that are in line with the principles and values of agroecology. (ALTIERI, 2012; ALTIERI; NICHOLLS, 2020; ALTIERI; TOLEDO, 2011; FRISON; CLÉMENT, 2020).

Research by Azevedo and Pelicioni (2011) brings a plural perspective of quality of life and health from forms of sustainable agriculture, where respondents included agroecology in this relationship and highlighted important aspects such as: agroecology as an instrument of *empowerment* and promotion of autonomy of farmers, health and the possibility of greater profits.

In this sense, agroecology emerges as a viable option, as an agro-food production system, which proposes food production within the principles of agrobiodiversity preservation and using less invasive methods.

Recognizing the relevance of agroecology in the Brazilian food context, there are public policies to encourage not only the consumption of these foods, but also their production. Reference should be made, in the interim, to Law n. 10,831 of 2003 and Decree n. 6,323 of 2007 that regulate the production, storage, labeling, transport, certification, commercialization and inspection of products. Complementarily, there is also a wide range of normative instructions, ordinances and resolutions that establish technical norms and procedures that govern the matter. Therefore, in addition to encouraging the production of healthy foods, the objective is to promote local development where biodiverse and quality products are offered directly to consumers, through free fairs, for example.

Other national public policies, focused on agroecology and health promotion, are the Food Acquisition Program (PAA - replaced by the Alimenta Brasil Program) and the National School Feeding Program (PNAE). Such initiatives provide for the purchase of food from family farming and targeting for school lunches, with school meals being a right of students and characterized as one of the FNS strategies. It is understood that offering quality food to students contributed to children's growth and biopsychosocial development, learning, school performance and the formation of healthy eating practices for children by offering meals that cover their nutritional needs during the school period and food and nutrition education actions (BRASIL, 2009). In this way, the public policy of the PNAE is consolidated as a tool that promotes the integration between farmers and quality food for students.

The Programa Alimenta Brasil, created by Provisional Measure 1,061, of August 9, 2021, converted into Law 14,284, of December 29, 2021, has two basic purposes: to promote access to food and encourage family farming. In replacement of the public policy called PAA, it is aimed at purchasing food, which aims to increase access to food and encourage production

by family farmers, extractivists, artisanal fishermen, indigenous peoples and other traditional populations.

The program is operationalized through the government, which buys food produced by family farmers and sends it to families in a situation of food insecurity, the social assistance network, public schools, health units, socio-educational and prison units, among others. (BRASIL, 2022). Alimenta Brasil also promotes food supply through government food purchases; strengthens local and regional circuits and marketing networks; values biodiversity and organic and agroecological food production; encourages healthy eating habits and encourages cooperativism and associations. (BRASIL, 2022)

Obviously, although such initiatives are important in the context of healthy eating and public health promotion, they are not enough to solve the problems involved. There is a need to increase incentives for sustainable production and, in fact, promote adequate food, in accordance with regulations issued by official bodies.

CONCLUSION

Promoting public health, agroecology and food security are related under different multidimensional meanings, whether in terms of improving the quality of life of the population, encouraging the production of diversified foods and within sustainable principles, or through safeguarding agrobiodiversity and other relevant environmental, social and economic aspects.

It is concluded that there is no health without adequate food, nutritionally dense and in sufficient quantity to provide the necessary calories, vitamins and minerals for the population. In addition, it is also about preventing serious diseases such as obesity, cancer and various comorbidities directly related to food.

On the other hand, encouraging sustainable agro-food systems such as agroecology promotes local economic development, as it encourages direct commercial relationships between producers and consumers, as well as fair prices for suppliers and customers.

We understand that vulnerabilities are growing both in relation to access to food itself, as well as the fight against hunger and poverty, which are increasing. However, it is up to the state, through public policies for the acquisition and distribution of food, to provide conditions for the food produced by small farmers to reach school lunches and the table of the population in a state of poverty. It is also up to all civil society to encourage healthy eating. It should be noted that in Brazil there are public policies aimed at these ends, but they are insufficient and, sometimes, ineffective.

We recognize that there are immense difficulties and of the most diverse meanings when it comes to proposing measures that ensure healthier eating behavior and it is up to the State to implement public policies that ensure healthy food, nutritionally rich, in sufficient quantity and produced within sustainable processes to all.

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